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THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN MELODIC AND DURATIONAL CONTOURS IN PROSODIC PROMINENCE AND PHRASING

A INTERAÇÃO ENTRE OS CONTORNOS MELÓDICO E DURACIONAL EM PROEMINÊNCIA E FRASEAMENTO PROSÓDICOS

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Abstract

Prosodic functions such as prominence and phrasing can be expressed in speech through durational and melodic modifications. However, research in this area has often focused on either duration or melody independently, with limited attention to their interaction as a functional unit. This is especially true for research on Brazilian Portuguese (BP), which, as a Romance language, is generally assumed to rely primarily on durational cues for the expression of prosodic functions. While this seems to hold for sentence-reading data, some studies indicate that it may not hold for more spontaneous forms of speech. Barbosa's 2008 article "Prominence- and boundary-related acoustic correlations in Brazilian Portuguese read and spontaneous speech" highlights this issue, presenting experimental results showing that melody also plays a role in BP prominence and phrasing. These findings align with Moraes's general description of BP intonation, found in Hirst and Di Cristo's 1998 "Intonation systems: a survey of twenty languages". This reveals two open questions in our understanding of the prosodic realization of prominence and phrasing: (1) how different prosodic parameters may interact; and (2) to what extent laboratory speech represents naturalistic speech patterns. The present study addresses these issues by analyzing the interplay between the melodic and durational parameters in the realization of terminal and non-terminal boundaries (as instances of prosodic phrasing) and narrow informational focus (as an instance of prosodic prominence), in a function-oriented experimental phonetic approach. The corpus used for this study consists of recordings of five male and five female native BP speakers from the state of São Paulo in an informal interview speech style that offers more spontaneous speech data to the analyses. To identify occurrences of the target prosodic functions, the recordings were divided into excerpts that were given to lay listeners trained to mark the words they perceived as realizations of (non-)terminal boundaries and narrow informational focus in their

corresponding orthographic transcriptions. Each excerpt was annotated by five listeners and a marked word was considered an effective realization of a target function if at least four agreed on its marking. Acoustic measurements were also extracted for parameters related to the melodic and durational contours. The interplay between these parameters was examined for the effective realizations of the target functions through cross-correlation analyses. The analyses reveal consistent correlations between the prosodic functions, duration peaks and an increase in F0 range. Moreover, terminal boundaries show a pre-stress melodic rise, followed by a fall on the stress, while non-terminal boundaries and occurrences of narrow informational focus show similar pre-stress lengthening patterns and melodic rises on the pre-stress V-V unit and on the stress itself. Additionally, foci also appear to show a significant fall after this rise. These findings suggest an interplay between melody and duration in the expression of prosodic prominence and phrasing. They also highlight the need to complement results obtained for sentence-reading data with those obtained for more spontaneous speech data, to assess the extent to which laboratory speech reflects naturalistic speech patterns and to observe these patterns when it does not fully reflect them.

Resumo

Funções prosódicas como proeminência e fraseamento podem ser expressas na fala através de alterações melódicas e duracionais. Contudo, a pesquisa na área tende a se focar ou na melodia, ou na duração, com atenção limitada à interação de ambas como unidade funcional. Isso é particularmente verdade quando se trata de pesquisas sobre o português brasileiro (PB), que, por ser uma língua românica, é geralmente visto como uma língua que se baseia principalmente em alterações duracionais para expressar funções prosódicas. Embora isso pareça se confirmar para dados de leitura de sentenças, alguns estudos indicam que esse pode não ser o caso para formas de fala mais espontâneas. O artigo de 2008 de Barbosa, “Prominence- and boundary-related acoustic correlations in Brazilian Portuguese read and spontaneous speech”, evidencia essa questão, apresentando resultados experimentais que mostram que a melodia também tem um papel na realização de proeminência e fraseamento em PB. Esses resultados estão alinhados com a descrição geral da entoação em PB feita por Moraes no livro “Intonation systems: a survey of twenty languages” de Hirst e Di Cristo, publicado em 1998. Isso revela duas questões em aberto no conhecimento a respeito da realização prosódica de proeminência e fraseamento: (1) como diferentes domínios prosódicos podem interagir; e (2) em que medida a fala de laboratório representa padrões da fala naturalística. O presente estudo aborda essas questões através de uma análise da interação

entre os domínios melódico e duracional na realização de fronteiras terminais e não-terminais (como instâncias de fraseamento prosódico) e foco informacional estreito (como instância de proeminência prosódica), numa abordagem fonética experimental de orientação funcional. O corpus utilizado nesse estudo consiste em gravações de cinco homens e cinco mulheres falantes nativos de PB do estado de São Paulo, num estilo de elocução de entrevista informal, que oferece dados de fala mais espontânea para as análises. Para identificar ocorrências das funções prosódicas sob análise, as gravações foram divididas em trechos enviados a ouvintes leigos que foram treinados para marcar as palavras que ouvissem como realizações de fronteiras (não) terminais e foco informacional estreito nas respectivas transcrições ortográficas. Cada trecho foi anotado por cinco ouvintes e uma palavra marcada foi considerada uma realização efetiva de uma função sob análise se pelo menos quatro concordaram com sua marcação. Medidas acústicas foram extraídas para parâmetros relacionados aos contornos melódico e duracional. A interação entre esses domínios foi examinada para as realizações efetivas das funções sob análise através de análises de correlação cruzada. As análises revelam correlações consistentes entre essas funções, picos locais de duração e maior intervalo de variação de F0. Além disso, fronteiras terminais apresentam subidas melódicas antes da tônica, seguidas por quedas na tônica, enquanto fronteiras não-terminais e ocorrências de foco informacional estreito apresentam padrões similares de alongamento antes da tônica e subidas melódicas na unidade V-V pretônica e na própria V-V tônica. Ademais, focos também parecem apresentar uma queda melódica significativa após essa subida. Esses resultados sugerem uma interação entre melodia e duração na expressão de proeminência e fraseamento prosódicos. Eles também destacam a necessidade de complementar resultados obtidos a partir de dados de leitura de sentenças com resultados obtidos a partir de dados de fala mais espontânea, a fim de avaliar em que medida a fala de laboratório reflete os padrões da fala naturalística e de observar esses padrões quando ela não os reflete completamente.

Keywords

Prominence. Phrasing. Melody. Duration.

Palavras-chave

Proeminência. Fraseamento. Melodia. Duração.

Lay Summary

Title: “How speech melody and rhythm act together to highlight words and signal if a speaker has finished an utterance or not”

When we speak, we use the rhythm and melody of our speech to convey important information to our listeners, such as which words we wish to emphasize and whether we have finished our utterances or not. But research in this area has often studied rhythm and melody separately, paying less attention to how rhythm and melody work together. This study addresses this question by investigating how rhythm and melody interact in words that listeners perceived as highlighted, indicating the end of an utterance or indicating a break within an utterance that is not yet finished. Our results indicate that highlighted words, utterance endings and breaks within utterances show longer sounds and wider pitch movements. Utterance endings also show melodic rises before the stress and falls on it, while breaks within utterances and highlighted words show characteristic sound lengthening patterns and pitch rises, which in highlighted words tend to be followed by pitch falls. These findings suggest that both rhythm and melody are important for understanding how meaning is structured in speech.

Introduction

Prosodic-acoustic parameters convey a variety of linguistic functions, such as the marking of linguistic units so they may be perceived as more salient than others, or the structuring of speech units into prosodic units larger than the syllable. These correspond, respectively, to the functions of prosodic prominence and phrasing, which are fundamental for the informational and prosodic organization of spoken utterances, as well as for the interpretation of their syntactic structure (Botinis; Granström; Möbius, 2001, p. 268; Cole; Mo; Baek, 2010; Hirst; Di Cristo, 1998, pp. 28-33; 34-36; Selkirk, 1984).

However, there is an open question in phonetic-linguistic knowledge regarding the prosodic realization of these functions. Most studies have focused either on durational or on melodic aspects of how prominence and phrasing are expressed in speech, and analyses of their interaction are either rare or lacking. This is especially true for BP and other Romance languages, often assumed to rely less on pitch accents than English and other Germanic languages for expressing these functions, and more on durational cues.

While this may hold for sentence reading, studies on BP indicate more prosodic boundaries and prominent units expressed through pitch accents in paragraph reading and spontaneous speech. This is shown by Barbosa (2008), who analyzed a corpus of spontaneous speech samples from radio interviews, and by Moraes (1998), who, in his chapter on BP

intonation, draws on data from previous studies on sentence and paragraph reading, as well as dialogues.

These findings also suggest that results may vary depending on the type of corpus used in phonetic-linguistic analyses. Yet research in the area has relied mainly on sentence reading, likely due to the inherent difficulty of working with more spontaneous forms of speech. This reliance may result in findings that do not fully represent spontaneous speech patterns.

Here we report the results of a research project designed to address these questions. This was achieved through an analysis of the melodic and durational contours in terminal and non-terminal boundaries (as instances of prosodic phrasing) and occurrences of narrow informational focus (as instances of prosodic prominence) in a spontaneous BP speech corpus. The following sections present a review of the literature that formed the basis of this research, state the hypotheses for the experiment, describe the methodology applied for extracting and analyzing the data, and present the results obtained.

1. A distinction between prosodic form and function

One way to conceptualize prosody is through a distinction between its function and form. Function refers to the communicative, expressive, and linguistic roles prosody plays in speech, such as realizing prominence and phrasing, while form refers to the realization of these functions through prosodic cues like rising or falling melody and syllable lengthening (Botinis; Granström; Möbius, 2001, pp. 267-269; 276; Hirst, 2005, pp. 337-338). For example, a distinction can be drawn between a falling F0 contour and a terminal boundary, even though they are often cross-linguistically associated. The former, a prosodic form, refers to continuous physical effects that can be apprehended through quantitative methods, while the latter, a prosodic function, refers to the qualitative linguistic meanings.

This distinction is useful because it clarifies that form and function belong to different spheres, and their relationship may not be a straightforward correspondence of one to the other. For example, the same form can express different functions, and a single function can be realized through multiple forms. This raises the question of which prosodic forms BP speakers employ to express specific functions: it should not be assumed that different functions cannot be expressed by similar forms, or that a function must be expressed through modifications in a single prosodic parameter; rather, further investigation is required to determine which forms are used and describe their characteristics.

The present study adopts this distinction between form and function. Therefore, its research objective was to investigate the melodic and durational features of items whose

properties were perceived by listeners as carriers of linguistic meaning.

2. Defining boundaries and focus

It is necessary to define what the terms “focus”, “terminal boundary” and “non-terminal boundary” mean in this research.

Based on Language Into Act Theory (L-Act Theory), an experimentally-based extension of Speech Act Theory, terminal boundaries are understood here as those boundaries that mark the end of an utterance, understood as the smallest pragmatically autonomous unit in speech and as corresponding to an accomplished speech act (see the appendix chapter in Raso and Mello, 2014 for an overview of L-Act Theory). Concisely, speech acts are actions performed through language, such as narrating an event, giving an order, or making a request, and the concept of speech acts highlights that speaking does not merely involve transmitting information, but also performing acts (an overview of Speech Act Theory and the contributions of key authors such as Austin and Searle can be found in Sadock, 2004).

Consequently, accomplished assertions, narrations, instructions, and similar acts correspond to complete utterances and may trigger the recognition of a terminal boundary by listeners. Conversely, a non-terminal boundary is a break within a complete utterance, at which point its corresponding speech act is not yet accomplished.

It is important to note that, depending on the theoretical basis upon which utterances and speech acts are defined, there may be speech acts that consist of more than one utterance. However, this is not the case in L-Act Theory, in which each utterance is seen as carrying an illocutionary force and, therefore, corresponding to an accomplished speech acts.

Focus appears to be a more complex term to define, as it has been defined in various and often conflicting ways by the literature. From a broad pragmatic perspective, focus can be defined as the introduction into discourse of information that is highlighted from the background, that is, from information already present in the discourse or at least presupposed by the speakers (Brunetti, 2004 for a discussion on possible definitions of focus). Moreover, many languages realize focus through forms spanning phonetic, phonological, morphological, syntactic and other levels of analysis. Therefore, different research approaches will account for different aspects of it, a probable reason for its many conflicting definitions.

A focused word or phrase can fulfill many roles in discourse, but the ones referred to as “informational focus” and “contrastive focus” have often received special attention. Broadly speaking, informational focus refers to focusing that presents an item as new information, assumed by the speaker to be unknown to the listener, and therefore highlighted

from the common background knowledge. Contrastive focus, in turn, refers to focusing that presents an item as contrasted with the listener's assumptions or what the speaker deems to be their assumptions (Zimmerman, 2008).

The nature of these two types of focus has been a source of debate, with some treating them as distinct interpretations of the same phenomenon (Bolinger, 1961; Rooth, 1992 for a unitary interpretation of focus), while others treat them as discrete categories encompassed by the umbrella term "focus" (Paoli, 2009, pp. 137-140; pp. 142-148). Lambrecht (1994), for instance, offers a unified view, defining focus as a relational property: the focused constituent establishes a relationship with the proposition it is a part of, whereby the proposition conveys new information. For the author, contrastivity is derived from the communicative context (pp. 286-291) and can be seen as gradual: every focused constituent is contrastive to the extent that it contrasts with a set of alternative items that could have occupied its place in the discourse. Contrastivity becomes more salient as the communicative context narrows and clarifies the paradigmatic set of alternatives.

Since the interest of this research lies in how prosodic forms convey functions in a communicatively relevant manner, it proposed to examine focus as a pragmatic-semantic phenomenon that requires prosodic expression, with its value (contrastive or informational) derived from the communicative context in which the focused word or phrase occurs. This approach follows a line similar to Lambrecht (1994).

Moreover, the instance of prominence chosen to be studied here is that of narrow informational focus, that is, words perceived as more prominent and not in a context evaluated as necessitating a contrastive interpretation. Informational focus was chosen because it is more likely to occur than contrastive focus, since it requires a specific communicative context to occur according to the definition adopted in this research.

3. The prosody of prominence and phrasing

This section reviews relevant literature on the cross-linguistic and BP-specific characteristics of the prosodic forms employed in the expression of prominence and phrasing.

3.1. Prominence and focus

Cross-linguistically, focused constituents tend to be realized with increased intensity, duration, and pitch range (Alzaidi et al., 2023; Cole et al., 2019; Im; Cole; Baumann, 2023; Xu, 2009, p. 920). Post-focal syllables tend to show pitch range compression and, in some cases, reduced duration and intensity, while pre-focal syllables tend to remain largely unaltered

(Alzaidi et al., 2023; Xu; Xu, 2005).

Similar prosodic characteristics are reported by works on BP, such as the previously mentioned chapter by Moraes (1998, p. 190). Truckenbrodt, Sandalo and Abaurre (2008), as well as Lucente and Barbosa (2008), report contours associated with focused words that include a rise in the pretonic syllable followed by a fall in the tonic and a low boundary tone, as well as a rise in the tonic followed by a fall in the post-tonic. Both contours include an expansion of pitch range resulting from their melodic movements.

These findings indicate that focused constituents tend to exhibit lengthening and pitch range expansion, are followed by a post-focal region affected by pitch range compression and, occasionally, duration compression, and are preceded by a largely unaltered pre-focal region.

3.2. Phrasing and (non-)terminality

Cross-linguistically, final falling melodic contours tend to convey the completeness of a unit, while final rising or non-low contours tend to convey incompleteness (Berkovits, 1984; Bolinger, 1998; Vaissière, 2005, pp. 247-248). Lengthening of the final element in a unit is also commonly associated with relaxation and ending (Vaissière, 2005, p. 245).

Therefore, terminal and non-terminal boundaries tend to involve lengthening and are associated with falling and rising melodic contours, respectively. However, BP declarative utterances tend to end in a melodic profile characterized by a peak in the pretonic syllable, followed by a fall in the final stressed syllable (Barbosa; Mareüil, 2016). This suggests that both boundary types in BP can involve a rising melodic component, indicating that other prosodic characteristics may be required to differentiate between them.

4. Objectives and hypotheses

This work aims to offer a contribution to experimental phonetics by examining how melody and duration interplay in the realization of prosodic functions, and which are the patterns of their interplay in a spontaneous speech corpus. This objective led the choice of methodology, hypotheses and theoretical background for this research.

Since spontaneous speech tends to occur in more naturalistic speech contexts, this research employed perceptual tests of lay listeners to identify occurrences of the functions under analysis, so the identified occurrences would be those that carry prosodic features relevant to the expression of these functions in naturalistic speech contexts. Moreover, boundaries are defined here with basis on L-Act Theory, which provides this research with a unit (the utterance, understood as the correlate of a speech act, delimited by terminal

boundaries and interrupted by non-terminal boundaries), that can be identified by lay listeners, since they are not acquainted with the linguistic notions of (non-)terminal boundaries, but are capable of identifying when a narration, assertion, instruction or any other speech act is accomplished and the utterance ends, or when the utterance was interrupted and the speech act has yet to be accomplished. Focus was similarly given a pragmatical definition. All of this means that, in the perceptual tests, lay listeners are asked to identify pragmatic functions, not specific prosodic forms, so the separation between function and form adopted by the research is maintained in the tests.

Finally, the hypotheses chosen for this research are based upon the patterns reported above in section 3. These hypotheses allow this paper to confront the results obtained by previous research, conducted for single prosodic parameters and/or non-spontaneous speech corpora, with the results for an analysis of the interplay between melody and duration in a spontaneous speech corpus. The following are the hypotheses of this research.

Regarding narrow informational focus:

- 1) The focal region will show duration increase and an expanded pitch range.
- 2) The post-focal region will show compression of pitch range and duration.
- 3) The pre-focal region will remain unaltered (i.e., show no evidence of compression).

Regarding (non-)terminal boundaries:

- 4) It will be possible to prosodically differentiate between terminal and non-terminal boundaries.
- 5) Terminal boundaries will show duration increase and a rising-falling F0 contour (a pre-stress rise followed by a fall in the stress).
- 6) Non-terminal boundaries will also show duration increase, but associated with a rising F0 contour.

5. Methodology

5.1. Corpus

The corpus used for this study consists of recordings kindly provided by the international project “A typology for word stress and speech rhythm based on acoustic and perceptual considerations” (Barbosa; Eriksson; Åkesson, 2013). The project comprises corpora in BP, British English, Estonian, French, German, Italian, and Swedish, recorded following a similar methodology, allowing for cross-linguistic comparisons.

For constructing the BP corpus, Barbosa, Eriksson and Åkesson (2013) recruited five

male and five female native BP speakers from the state of São Paulo, with complete or ongoing higher education and ages between 21 and 30 years for the male speakers, and 18 and 26 for the female speakers. The participants were recorded in three speech styles (informal interview, sentence reading and word list reading), in PCM (WAV) at a sample rate of 16 kHz. For our research, only the informal interview recordings were used.

In each interview, interviewer and interviewee were close friends, allowing for monologues, less monitored and more spontaneous speech on the part of the interviewee. The interviews lasted approximately 15 minutes each.

5.2. Perceptual Testing

In this research, words under narrow informational focus and realizing (non-)terminal boundaries were identified through perceptual testing conducted with lay listeners. The primary aim was to identify prosodic events capable of expressing these functions in naturalistic speech contexts.

As it would not be reasonable to expect a listener to effectively annotate a set of ten 15-minute recordings, the interviews were divided into smaller excerpts of approximately 250 words for the perceptual testing. In total, 77 excerpts were obtained. Each excerpt received a matching orthographic transcription without punctuation marks, capital letters, or paragraph divisions, so that listeners would not be influenced by orthographic conventions.

A total of 30 native BP speakers were recruited based on the following criteria: they had to be native to the state of São Paulo and have spent most of their lives there; be between 20 and 50 years old; not be affected by any pathology or condition that could impair their auditory perception; and have no formal training in linguistics or prosodic annotation. All of these criteria were verified through self-report.

To ensure that all excerpts were annotated five times, each listener was assigned twelve to thirteen excerpts. Annotating a single excerpt took about thirty minutes, and listeners were instructed not to annotate more than one excerpt consecutively. Most listeners annotated one excerpt every couple of days according to their time availability, taking approximately one month to complete their participation.

5.2.1. Training sessions

Following a procedure similar to those adopted by Cole, Mo and Baek (2010), and Barbosa (2010), each listener underwent a brief training session in which they were instructed on how to annotate their assigned excerpts.

Training sessions were conducted individually for all speakers through video conferencing platforms. Each listener was guided through the annotation procedure using a training audio excerpt accompanied by its corresponding transcription, which was shared by the researcher through the platform. Instructions were given step by step.

The first step was to listen to the audio and mark, with an asterisk (*) in the transcription, the words perceived as “enfáticas pelo falante” (“emphasized by the speaker”, i.e., focused words). The second step was to listen to the audio again and mark, with a forward slash (/) in the transcription, words perceived as indicating “o fim de um enunciado completo” (“the end of a complete utterance”, i.e., a terminal boundary), and with a plus sign (+), words perceived as indicating “uma quebra num enunciado completo” (“a break within a complete utterance”, i.e., a non-terminal boundary).

After the instructions for each step, the researcher played the first sentences of the audio and provided an example annotation of the step’s corresponding function(s). The listener was then asked to identify words perceived as realizing the function(s) in other portions of the excerpt.

Once the training session was completed, listeners were asked to annotate the full training excerpt by themselves. After the annotation of this excerpt was completed and sent back to the researcher, it was examined by the researcher in private, to verify whether it showed reasonable overlap with the researcher’s own perception of (non-)terminal boundaries and occurrences of narrow informational focus for the corresponding audio excerpt. While perfect correspondence between an individual’s annotation and the perceptions of another cannot be expected, some degree of overlap can, given that prosodic functions are linguistic categories and, as such, are not subject to high variability among speakers of the same language.

If overlap was observed, the training was considered successful and the listener proceeded to the annotation of the twelve to thirteen excerpts assigned to them. After submitting each annotated excerpt, the listener received the next one, until all excerpts had been annotated.

There was only one case of unsuccessful training. To avoid asymmetries between participants’ training conditions, this participant was not retrained, but excluded from the research. A new participant was then contacted, trained, evaluated, and assigned to annotate the excerpts that the excluded participant would have annotated, had that participant’s training been considered successful.

Each group of ten listeners was trained using different audio excerpts and

transcriptions from the corpus. This ensured that listeners were trained with materials drawn from the corpus used for this research (therefore matching the speech style and situation of the excerpts assigned to them) and that excerpts used for training were annotated by listeners who had not been trained on them.

5.2.2. Effective realization of prosodic functions

The degree of agreement among listeners' annotations was considered an index of the realization of prosodic functions. As each excerpt was annotated by five listeners, proportion tests with continuity correction were conducted in R (R Core Team, 2024) using the `prop.test()` function to test whether words marked by multiple listeners as realizing a function differed significantly from words that received no markings for this function.

The proportion tests yielded a p-value of 0.0528 ($\chi^2(1) = 3.75$) for the comparison between a word being marked by four listeners and a word not being marked by any listener. As this value is close to the adopted significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), words marked by at least four listeners as realizing a function were considered to differ significantly from words unmarked for that function, indicating that they realized it in a communicatively relevant manner. Accordingly, words marked by four or five listeners as realizing a certain function were considered effective realizations of this function.

All 77 audio excerpts were then re-examined with attention to the communicative context of each occurrence of focus marked by at least four listeners. Occurrences found in contexts evaluated by the researcher as implying a contrastive interpretation were excluded from the analyses, as the instance of prosodic prominence chosen to be analyzed in this study is informational focus.

Table 1 reports the number of effective realizations of (non-)terminal boundaries and occurrences of narrow informational focus encountered for female speakers, male speakers, and for the pooled data set.

	INTERVIEW RECORDINGS		
	FEMALE	MALE	POOLED
TERMINAL BOUNDARIES	147	103	250
NON-TERMINAL BOUNDARIES	58	73	131
NARROW INFORMATIONAL FOCUS	514	450	964

Table 1. Occurrences of (non-)terminal boundaries and narrow informational focus

Table 1 shows that the number of effective realizations of narrow informational focus is considerably larger than that of either type of boundary, in line with the expectation that nearly all sentences in the corpus contain at least one word under informational focus.

Interestingly, the number of effective realizations of non-terminal boundaries is smaller than that of terminal boundaries, despite the expectation that more non-terminal boundaries would be encountered, resulting from the inherently continuous nature of spontaneous speech, marked by hesitations, re-elaborations, and pauses.

It is important to consider that lay listeners may perceive words as terminal for various reasons, even when they are not pragmatically terminal. Therefore, one could hypothesize that this unexpected proportion is due to misidentified terminal boundaries inflating the terminal set. However, this does not seem to be the case. First, the numbers in Table 1 refer only to occurrences of prosodic functions with significant listener agreement, that is, words marked as realizing a same function by at least four out of five listeners, so misidentified terminals could only enter the set of effective realizations if perceived as such by at least four out of five listeners, which already reduces their chance of doing so. Moreover, the training sessions followed a procedure already employed and shown to be successful in previous research, which reduces the chance that successfully trained participants would misidentify functions, or that they would do so consistently enough, and for a sufficiently similarly set of words, such that the proportions of effective realizations would be significantly altered.

Hence, this hypothesis is discarded as an explanation for the break in expectations mentioned above. Furthermore, these arguments also indicate that it is unlikely that enough misidentified terminals or functions in general exist to skew the analyzes that follow.

An alternative explanation is that, since these numbers refer only to occurrences of prosodic functions with significant listener agreement, it may be the case that listeners showed greater agreement when marking terminal boundaries than non-terminal boundaries.

Consequently, after filtering out words marked by fewer than four listeners, terminal boundaries show more effective realizations than non-terminal boundaries. This is supported by the coherence analyses in section 6.1.

5.3. Coherence analyses

In order to statistically verify whether listener training was effective (that is, whether agreement between listeners was greater than chance), the annotations produced by each group of five listeners assigned to the same excerpts were subjected to Krippendorff's alpha and Fleiss' kappa tests of inter-rater reliability. Employing both tests serves to ensure the robustness of the results across different reliability metrics.

Krippendorff's alpha is a statistical measure of inter-rater agreement for a set of items. The alpha coefficient ranges from -1 to 1 , where 1 indicates perfect agreement, 0 indicates agreement at chance level, and -1 indicates systematic disagreement. Fleiss's kappa is likewise a measure of inter-rater reliability, but unlike Krippendorff's alpha, it assumes categorical data and requires that all raters evaluate the same set of items. Kappa values are commonly interpreted using conventional thresholds, with higher values indicating stronger agreement. These tests were conducted in R via the irr package, which allows for the use of the functions `kripp.alpha()` and `kappam.fleiss()`.

For the coherence analyses, three matrices were generated for each group of five listeners assigned to the same twelve to thirteen excerpts, corresponding to the three functions analyzed in this study. Each matrix had one row for each word of all excerpts assigned to the group, and one column for each of the group's five listeners. Entries were coded as either a 1 or a 0 , indicating whether a listener rated a word as realizing a function (1) or not (0).

5.4. Acoustic analyses

For the acoustic analyses, all audio excerpts were automatically segmented into phones using the Montreal Forced Aligner (Mcauliffe et al., 2017), a forced aligner that runs from the command line within the Conda environment and generates Praat TextGrids for audio files in supported languages. The only purpose of this segmentation into phones was to allow for the derivation of a segmentation into V-V units from it. A new tier was added in Praat (Boersma; Weenink, 2024) to each TextGrid containing its corresponding segmentation into V-V units.

Figure 1 below shows the word "Morumbi" (the name of a neighborhood in the city of São Paulo) segmented into phones (middle tier) and V-V units (lower tier) in Praat. Segmentation errors by the forced aligner were manually corrected for the V-V unit

segmentation, since all measurements in the analyses of this research were extracted for the V-V units.

Figure 1. Segmentation of a word into phones and V-V units

As shown in Figure 1, V-V units are defined as sequences of phones occurring between the onset of a vowel and the onset of the following vowel (Barbosa, 2006, p. 30). These units have already been shown by experimental research to be important for speech perception and production (see the second chapter in Barbosa, 2006 for an overview of relevant literature). Since listeners' perceptions were used to identify the realization of prosodic functions in this research, a prosodic unit that reflected their perception was also chosen to be analyzed.

Values of acoustic parameters related to durational and melodic contours were extracted for the V-V units using the Prosody Descriptor Extractor script (Barbosa, 2021), a Praat script that computes values for prosodic-acoustic parameters related to melody, rhythm and voice quality from audio files and their corresponding Praat TextGrids, in conjunction with a reference file providing mean and standard deviation values for phone duration in the target language for normalization. The script normalizes the V-V duration contour with z-scores and smooths it using a five-point weighted moving average (Barbosa, 2007, pp. 80-81; Barbosa, 2008), while the melodic curve is smoothed by Praat. The script was run in Praat for each audio excerpt, using its corresponding Praat TextGrid and the BP phone duration reference file. F0 calculation thresholds were set between 75 and 400 Hz for male speakers and between 100 and 500 Hz for female speakers.

Values were extracted for the following parameters:

- ***duration_ms***: raw (non-normalized, non-smoothed) duration of V-V units.
- ***sg_edge***: occurrence of local duration peaks associated with stress group edges. This parameter is obtained through the SG Detector algorithm, also embedded in the Prosody Descriptor Extractor. The SG Detector automatically detects duration peaks from normalized and smoothed duration values, assigning a 1 to a V-V unit if it is a duration peak, and a 0 if it is not. Manual correction may be required. The parameter containing the assignment of each V-V unit as a local duration peak or not is named “boundary” in the output files generated by the script, but here it was renamed to “sg_edge” to avoid confusion with (non-)terminal boundaries.
- ***f0med***: F0 median values in Hz.
- ***f0range***: F0 range values in Hz. This parameter is not provided by the script, but can easily be calculated by subtracting F0 minimum values from F0 maximum values, which are parameters provided by the script. It indicates how much F0 varies at a certain point in time.
- ***df0posmean***: 1st-derivative F0 mean in Hertz/frame of the positive derivatives. A measure of the F0 rise rate.
- ***df0negmean***: 1st-derivative F0 mean in Hertz/frame of the negative derivatives. A measure of the F0 fall rate.

The Prosody Descriptor Extractor script generates output files containing the measures extracted for all parameters included in the script, for all V-V units in all audio files. These files were merged, unused parameters were removed, and three new columns were added to record all effective realizations of each prosodic function analyzed in this study. The stressed V-V unit in an effective realization of a prosodic function was assigned a 1 in the corresponding function column, while all other V-V units were assigned a 0.

Cross-correlation analyses were conducted in R. Cross-correlation is a statistical technique used to identify patterns in the behavior of one variable in relation to another across their entire value series, indicating whether changes in one series tend to precede, coincide with, or follow changes in the other, making cross-correlation tests suitable for analyzing modifications in the melodic and durational contours that occur before, during, or after a prosodic function.

However, it was not possible to use R’s `ccf()` function for the cross-correlation analyses, since it requires complete series of data to operate and the series of measurements

for the parameters $df0_{posmean}$ and $df0_{negmean}$ contained scattered NA values. Reducing the data set to NA-free segments would not be feasible, as this would significantly reduce the amount of data used for the analyses, discarding many occurrences of prosodic functions which showed NA values for only one or two of its V-V units.

To address this issue, a custom R function (Sprogis, 2026) was developed to compute cross-correlations following Pearson's method (the same used by the `ccf()` function) using only valid (not NA) observations at each lag and to calculate approximate significance limits (given by $\pm 2/\sqrt{n}$) based on the number of observations used for calculating cross-correlations at each lag.

6. Results

The results obtained for the analyses are reported the following subsections.

6.1. Agreement between listeners

The following table informs the results obtained in the coherence analyses for each group of five listeners assigned to the same twelve to thirteen audio excerpts.

Group	Prosodic function	Krippendorff's alpha	Fleiss' kappa
Group 1 13 excerpts 3443 total words	Focus	0.403	0.403 (z = 74.8, p ≈ 0)
	Terminal	0.604	0.604 (z = 112, p ≈ 0)
	Non-terminal	0.255	0.255 (z = 47.3, p ≈ 0)
Group 2 13 excerpts 3443 total words	Focus	0.386	0.386 (z = 71.5, p ≈ 0)
	Terminal	0.518	0.518 (z = 96.1, p ≈ 0)
	Non-terminal	0.284	0.284 (z = 52.6, p ≈ 0)
Group 3 13 excerpts 3402 total words	Focus	0.424	0.424 (z = 78.2, p ≈ 0)
	Terminal	0.457	0.457 (z = 84.3, p ≈ 0)
	Non-terminal	0.284	0.284 (z = 52.4, p ≈ 0)
Group 4 13 excerpts 3414 total words	Focus	0.396	0.396 (z = 73.2, p ≈ 0)
	Terminal	0.624	0.624 (z = 115, p ≈ 0)
	Non-terminal	0.175	0.175 (z = 32.4, p ≈ 0)
Group 5 13 excerpts 3301 total words	Focus	0.352	0.352 (z = 63.9, p ≈ 0)
	Terminal	0.446	0.446 (z = 81, p ≈ 0)
	Non-terminal	0.243	0.243 (z = 44.2, p ≈ 0)
Group 6 12 excerpts 3067 total words	Focus	0.472	0.472 (z = 82.7, p ≈ 0)
	Terminal	0.562	0.562 (z = 98.5, p ≈ 0)
	Non-terminal	0.199	0.199 (z = 34.9, p ≈ 0)

Table 2. Krippendorff's alpha and Fleiss' kappa values for all groups' classification of words as realizing prosodic functions

As shown in Table 2, the alpha and kappa values are identical to each other for all groups and all functions. This result is expected in cases in which Krippendorff's alpha is calculated for a nominal variable and all raters evaluate the same items. This is the case of this research.

Given that the p-value is approximately 0 in all cases, the null hypothesis that the true kappa value is zero (i.e., inter-rater agreement is not greater than chance) is rejected for all groups, and the alternative hypothesis that kappa is different from zero, indicating agreement beyond chance, is accepted. These results suggest that the methodology applied to train listeners to annotate prosodic functions was effective.

For all groups of five listeners, the alpha and kappa values follow the same order, from higher to lower: terminal boundaries, informational focus, and non-terminal boundaries. This pattern indicates that listeners show the highest agreement when identifying terminal

boundaries, followed by focused words, and the lowest (but still statistically significant) agreement when identifying non-terminal boundaries.

6.2. Cross-correlation analyses

The results of the cross-correlation analyses are represented in the following bar graphs. In these graphs, bars indicate cross-correlation coefficient values and capped vertical lines indicate the upper and lower limits of approximate significance intervals. Correlation coefficient values inside these limits have a probability greater than the adopted α of 0.05 of occurring under the null hypothesis that the true cross-correlation at each lag is actually zero. Conversely, all correlation coefficient values outside these limits have a probability equal to or lower than 0.05 of occurring under this hypothesis, in which case the alternative hypothesis of a non-zero cross-correlation between the series of values is accepted.

In the graphs, the X-axis represents lag values, indicating how many V-V units one series is shifted relative to the other, while the Y-axis represents correlation coefficient values.

Cross-correlations were calculated only for lags from -2 to 2 . This choice was motivated by two reasons. First, previous pilot tests indicated that significant correlations tend to occur at most two V-V units before or after the function's stressed V-V unit. Second, significant correlations found before or after these lags may actually reflect modifications associated with a preceding or following function.

6.2.1. Correlations for terminal boundaries

This subsection presents correlations between terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters. Figures 2, 3, and 4 present the results for the pooled, female, and male groups, respectively.

Figure 2. Cross-correlations between terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters for the pooled group

Figure 3. Cross-correlations between terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters for the female group

Figure 4. Cross-correlations between terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters for the male group

Concerning durational aspects, the correlations found for the pooled group are consistent with a durational profile characterized by an increase in raw V-V duration at the boundary's stressed V-V unit (significant positive correlation with `duration_ms` at lag 0), which also tends to be the stress group's duration peak (significant positive correlation with `sg_edge` at lag 0). The following two V-V units tend not to be duration peaks (significant negative correlations with `sg_edge` at lags 1 and 2), and the second V-V unit after the stress shows a decrease in raw duration (significant negative correlation with `duration_ms` at lag 2). The pre-stress V-V unit also tends to be a duration peak (significant positive correlation with

sg_edge at lag -1). The female and male groups exhibit similar patterns, although the female group does not show a decrease in raw V-V duration two V-V units after the stress.

Concerning melodic aspects, Figure 2 shows that the correlations found for the pooled group are consistent with a melodic profile characterized by higher F0 values two V-V units before the stress (significant positive correlation with f0med at lag -2), followed by a melodic fall at the pre-stress V-V unit (significant negative correlation with df0negmean at lag -1). A rise possibly begins there and continues at the boundary's stressed V-V unit (significant positive correlations with df0posmean at lag 0), where another melodic fall occurs (significant negative correlation with df0negmean at lag 0). The two post-stress V-V units show evidence of a compression of F0 range (significant negative correlations with f0range at lags 1 and 2).

Figure 3 shows that the female group exhibits almost no significant correlations with melodic parameters at lags other than lag 0, suggesting these female speakers realized terminal boundaries with some considerable melodic variability, so that fewer significant correlations can be observed. The male group (Figure 4) shows significant correlations consistent with a melodic profile similar to the one described for the pooled group. The main differences are that the male group also shows a melodic fall at the post-stress V-V unit (significant negative correlation with df0negmean at lag 1), while no fall is observed at the stress itself. Despite this, a significant negative correlation with f0med at lag 0 indicates lower F0 values to be found at the stressed V-V unit for the male group.

Figure 5 shows an example of a word that shows patterns consistent with those described for terminal boundaries.

Figura 5: Example of melodic and durational contours for terminal boundaries

This word, “fevereiro” (“February”), taken from a female speaker’s interview in the corpus of this study, provides an example of the melodic and durational patterns reported for terminal boundaries. From top to bottom, Figure 5 shows the melodic contour (smoothed for better visualization), the orthographic transcription, its phonological segmentation, and the segmentation into V-V units.

Consistent with the durational pattern described above, the stressed “eR” V-V unit appears to show increased duration compared to other V-V units, while the unstressed “U” is shorter than all other units, indicating it is not a local duration peak. Figure 5 also illustrates rises and falls consistent with the melodic pattern described above, including higher values two V-V units before the stress, a rise and a fall in the pre-stress V-V unit, a fall in the “eR” V-V unit, and a compressed F0 profile in the post-stress “U” V-V unit.

6.2.2. Correlations for non-terminal boundaries

This subsection presents correlations found between non-terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters. Figures 6, 7, and 8 present the results for the pooled, female, and male groups, respectively.

Figure 6. Cross-correlations between non-terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters for the pooled group

Figure 7. Cross-correlations between non-terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters for the female group

Figure 8. Cross-correlations between non-terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters for the male group

Concerning durational aspects, the correlations found for the pooled group are consistent with a durational profile characterized by increased raw V-V duration at the stressed V-V unit and the two V-V units before it (significant positive correlations with duration_ms at lags -2 to 0). The stressed V-V unit also tends to be the stress group's duration peak (significant positive correlation with sg_edge at lag 0), while the following two V-V units tend not to be duration peaks (significant negative correlations with sg_edge at lags 1 and 2). Figures 7 and 8 show that the female and male groups display similar patterns, except for the female group not showing significant negative correlations with sg_edge or a

significant positive correlation with duration_ms at lag -2.

Interestingly, for the pooled, female and male groups the correlation with raw V-V duration increase at lag 0 is stronger than the correlation with stress group duration peaks at the same lag.

Concerning melodic aspects, the significant correlations found for the pooled group are consistent with a melodic profile characterized by an F0 fall at the pre-stress V-V unit (significant negative correlation with df0negmean at lag -1), followed by a rise at the boundary's stress (significant positive correlation with df0posmean at lag 0). Both the female and male groups exhibit similar melodic patterns, but the female group differs by showing a significant positive correlation with df0posmean at lag -1, indicating that its non-terminal rise begins before the stress, while the male group differs by not showing a significant negative correlation with df0negmean at lag -1.

Figure 9 shows an example of a word that shows patterns consistent with those described for non-terminal boundaries.

Figure 9: Example of melodic and durational contours for non-terminal boundaries

This word, “gostava” (“used to like”), taken from a male speaker’s interview in the

corpus of this study, provides an example of the durational and melodic patterns reported above for non-terminal boundaries. From top to bottom, Figure 9 shows the melodic contour (smoothed for better visualization), the orthographic transcription, its phonological segmentation, and the segmentation into V-V units.

Consistent with the durational pattern described above, the pre-stress “oSt” and stressed “av” V-V units show increased duration if compared to the unstressed “A” V-V unit, which is shorter and not a local duration peak. Figure 9 also shows a melodic rise at the stressed “av” V-V unit consistent with the one described for non-terminal boundaries.

6.2.3. Correlations for narrow informational focus

This subsection presents correlations between occurrences of narrow informational focus and prosodic parameters. Figures 10, 11, and 12 present the results for the pooled, female, and male groups, respectively.

Figure 10. Cross-correlations between occurrences of narrow informational focus and prosodic parameters for the pooled group

Figure 11. Cross-correlations between occurrences of narrow informational focus and prosodic parameters for the female group

Figure 12. Cross-correlations between occurrences of narrow informational focus and prosodic parameters for the male group

Similar to the results described above for non-terminal boundaries, the pooled group shows a durational profile characterized by increased raw V-V duration at the stressed V-V unit and the two V-V units before it (significant positive correlations with duration_ms at lags -2 to 0). The stressed V-V unit also tends to be the stress group's duration peak (significant positive correlation with sg_edge at lag 0), while the surrounding V-V units tend not to be duration peaks (significant negative correlations with sg_edge at lags -2, -1, 1, and 2). The second post-stress V-V unit shows a decrease in raw duration (significant negative correlation with duration_ms at lags 2).

Figures 11 and 12 indicate that the female and male groups show similar durational patterns, except for the female group not showing a significant positive correlation with `duration_ms` at lag -2, and the male group not showing a significant negative correlation with `sg_edge` at lag -2.

Concerning melodic aspects, Figure 10 shows that the correlations found for the pooled group are consistent with a melodic profile characterized by a significant low point two V-V units before the stress (significant negative correlation with `f0med` at lag -2), followed by an F0 rise in the pre-stress V-V unit that continues at the boundary's stress (significant positive correlations with `df0posmean` at lags -1 and 0). A fall occurs there and continues at the post-stress V-V unit (significant negative correlations with `df0negmean` at lags 0 and 1). Higher F0 values are also observed at the post-stress V-V unit (significant positive correlation with `f0med` at lag 1), followed by a somewhat compressed F0 curve two V-V units after the stress (significant negative correlation with `f0range` at lag 2).

Figures 11 and 12 show that the male and female groups show similar melodic profiles to those described above. The main difference for the male group is the presence of a significant negative correlation with `df0negmean` at lag -1, and its absence at lag 1. This absence is also observed for the female group at the same lag.

Figure 13 shows an example of a word that shows patterns consistent with those described for occurrences of narrow informational focus.

Figura 13: Example of melodic and durational contours for occurrences of narrow informational focus

This sentence, “é bem básico” (“it’s very basic”), taken from a female speaker’s interview in the corpus of this study, provides an example of the durational and melodic patterns reported for occurrences of narrow informational focus in the word “básico” (“basic”). From top to bottom, Figure 13 shows the melodic contour (smoothed for better visualization), the orthographic transcription, its phonological segmentation, and the segmentation into V-V units.

Consistent with the durational pattern described above, the pre-stress “eNb” and stressed “az” V-V units show increased duration if compared to the surrounding V-V units, which are shorter and are not duration peaks. Figure 13 also illustrates the melodic pattern observed for occurrences of narrow informational focus, including a significant low point two V-V units before the stress, a rise at the pre-stress V-V unit, a fall at the stressed “az” V-V unit, and a relatively high and compressed F0 curve two V-V units after the stress (at the unstressed “U”).

7. Discussion

Concerning the coherence analyses, a result worth discussing is the order of the alpha and

kappa values observed across all groups of five listeners, which indicates that listeners show the highest agreement when identifying terminal boundaries, followed by focused words and non-terminal boundaries.

It is possible that this result reflects differences in the consistency of prosodic cues. It may be the case that functions that are marked more consistently are more easily identifiable and result in higher listener agreement, while functions that exhibit greater variability are harder to identify, resulting in lower listener agreement. If this is the case, terminal boundaries appear to be the prosodic function that shows the most consistent prosodic cues, while non-terminal boundaries appear to be more variable, explaining why listeners showed lower agreement when marking them.

Regarding the cross-correlation analyses, the results were consistent with melodic and durational patterns associated with some interesting characteristics that are also worth discussing.

Terminal boundaries show significant correlations consistent with a durational profile characterized by an increase in raw V-V duration at the boundary's stressed V-V unit, which also tends to be the stress group's duration peak. This is followed by a post-stress V-V unit which tends not to be a duration peak and by a V-V unit which shows raw duration decrease. An interesting finding is that the pre-stress V-V unit also tends to be a duration peak, suggesting that there may be some cases in which the duration peak of a stress group is the pre-stress V-V unit of a terminal boundary and the boundary's stressed V-V unit is not the duration peak of the following stress group.

Significant correlations for terminal boundaries are also consistent with a melodic profile characterized by higher F0 values two V-V units before the stress, followed by a melodic fall at the pre-stress V-V unit, where a rise may begin and continue at the boundary's stressed V-V unit. Another melodic fall occurs at this point, followed by two V-V units which show a compressed F0 curve. This pattern parallels the profile reported by Barbosa and Mareüil (2016) for BP declarative utterances discussed in the review of relevant literature in section 3.2.

Non-terminal boundaries show significant correlations consistent with a durational profile characterized by an increase in raw V-V duration at the stressed V-V unit and the two units coming before. The stressed V-V unit also tends to be the stress group's duration peak. Different from other functions, raw V-V duration increase at the stressed V-V unit appears to be more consistently correlated with non-terminal boundaries than the stressed V-V unit being a local duration peak.

This finding is puzzling. One might expect that a qualitative difference in duration (such as the presence or absence of a local duration peak associated with the end of a stress group) would more consistently prompt listeners to identify words as realizing some function that is at least partly conveyed through durational cues than quantitative differences in raw V-V duration. Nevertheless, it may be the case that the continuous and quantitative aspect of duration is also informative in non-terminal boundaries: while the presence of a local duration peak is clearly associated with non-terminal boundaries, as shown by the results of this research, the extent to which a peak is lengthened may also contribute to induce the perception of non-finality in the listener.

Significant correlations for non-terminal boundaries are also consistent with a melodic profile characterized by an F0 fall at the pre-stress V-V unit, followed by a rise at the stressed V-V unit, similar to the rise commonly associated with non-terminal boundaries in the literature.

The fact that terminal boundaries, associated with falling contours, and non-terminal boundaries, associated with rising contours, also show significant correlations consistent with a rise and a fall preceding these contours may indicate that both boundary types involve preparatory melodic movements. These movements may anticipate the subsequent melodic gestures and make them more prominent, resulting in a rise that prepares a more prominent fall in terminal boundaries, and a fall that prepares a more prominent rise in non-terminal boundaries.

Finally, occurrences of narrow informational focus show significant correlations consistent with a durational profile similar to the one reported above for non-terminal boundaries. The only difference is that the presence of a duration peak at the focused word's stressed V-V unit is more consistently correlated with occurrences of narrow informational focus than raw V-V duration increase.

This similarity in lengthening patterns may reflect a common property of non-terminal boundaries and occurrences of narrow informational focus. For example, both functions may share a "call for attention" property, either because a word conveys important new information (in the case of occurrences of narrow informational focus), or because the speaker intends to maintain the turn and makes use of a resource that maintains the listener's attention (in the case of non-terminal boundaries). A similar shared property could explain why a similar durational profile is observed for both functions.

Significant correlations for occurrences of narrow informational focus are also consistent with a melodic profile characterized by a low point two V-V units before the stress,

followed by a rise at the pre-stress V-V unit that continues into the stressed V-V unit. A fall begins at the stress and continues at the post-stress V-V unit, where higher F0 values appear to occur, followed by a somewhat compressed F0 curve two V-V units after the stress.

Comparing these prosodic profiles, it appears that modifications in more than one prosodic parameter are necessary to distinguish between their associated functions. While terminal boundaries show a distinct rising-falling melodic pattern, occurrences of narrow informational focus show a somewhat similar contour. To fully differentiate between these two functions, it is necessary to consider the distinct lengthening pattern associated with narrow informational focus. However, a similar lengthening pattern is also observed in non-terminal boundaries, and distinguishing these from occurrences of narrow informational focus requires attention to differences in their melodic profiles. Finally, although terminal and non-terminal boundaries show distinct melodic profiles, both share a rising melodic component at a similar position. Consequently, a full characterization of both boundary types should also take into account their durational profiles.

Another result worth discussing is that the female group appears to show a smaller number of V-V units (or lags) for which significant correlations with melodic and durational parameters are observed, if compared to the male and pooled groups. This may indicate that the female speakers in this corpus employed more varied melodic and durational profiles than male speakers for signaling prosodic functions, resulting in fewer significant correlations in the analyses. A factor that could motivate increased variation is emotional expressiveness; as documented by literature on the subject, female adults tend to show increased emotional expressiveness when compared to their male peers (see Chaplin, 2015), which could result in increased intra-speaker variation for female speakers. However, this is only a possible interpretation of the results and any further consideration would be speculative.

8. Conclusion

This study investigated the interplay between melody and duration in the realization of (non-)terminal boundaries and narrow informational focus. The main objectives of this research were to investigate how different prosodic parameters interact in signaling prosodic functions and to complement the findings of previous literature with results from more spontaneous speech data.

We identified clear melodic and durational patterns associated with the prosodic functions under study, highlighting both the importance and the feasibility of using spontaneous or semi-spontaneous speech corpora for analyzing prosodic functions.

Regarding narrow informational focus, our findings show that the focal region (understood as the stressed V-V unit of a focused word) exhibits increased duration and an expanded pitch range, confirming our first hypothesis. The post-focal region exhibits pitch range and duration compression (observed only for the second V-V unit following the stress), confirming our second hypothesis. The pre-focal region remains largely unaltered (shows no evidence of compression), confirming our third hypothesis.

Regarding (non-)terminal boundaries, our findings show that the two boundary types can be prosodically differentiated, confirming our fourth hypothesis. Terminal boundaries exhibit an increase in duration (at the boundary's stressed V-V unit) and show correlations consistent with a rising-falling F0 contour, confirming our fifth hypothesis. Non-terminal boundaries exhibit an increase in duration (at the stressed V-V unit and the previous two units) and show correlations consistent with a rising F0 contour, confirming our sixth hypothesis.

It is important to note that the results do not point to any specific melodic profile, but point to some profiles with which they are consistent. This is due to the fact that correlation values calculated for V-V units can only capture the overall behavior within these units, whereas melodic profiles are continuous by nature and occur across V-V units. Hence, a certain level of interpretation was inevitable to infer melodic profiles consistent with our results.

Finally, the results indicate that both melodic and durational characteristics are necessary to characterize prosodic functions. This suggests a systematic interplay between melody and duration and that prosodic functions are not associated with uni-dimensional forms. Instead, prosodic functions are expressed through modifications in a multidimensional phonic substance, which consequently assumes forms spanning melody and duration. Future research into voice quality changes associated with these functions may serve to further elucidate the multidimensionality of these forms.

9. Acknowledgments

The author thanks Plinio A. Barbosa for sharing the audio files analyzed in this research. The author also thanks the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) for supporting this research through the grant of a Master's scholarship.

10. Competing Interests

The author declares no competing interests.

11. Data Availability Statement

Part of the research data are publicly available in an online repository and the pathway to access it is described in the next paragraph. Other data are available under controlled access and the pathway and conditions to access it are explained in the third and fourth paragraphs. The last paragraph details how a reviewer/editor may access restricted data needed for editorial/peer review.

The custom R function developed to compute cross-correlations from valid observations and approximate confidence intervals for each lag, as well as information on how to run it, are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18786920>. These materials are made available under CC BY 4.0. The address <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18803206> contains a minimum reproducibility package for reproducing the cross-correlation bar graphs encountered at the results section above, including an R script for generating bar graphs with the tidyverse R library, and the final cross-correlation result tables used to generate each cross-correlation figure. This minimum reproducibility package does not include the .txt file containing the series of effective realization of prosodic functions derived from listeners' annotations and the .txt file containing acoustic measures extracted from the audio files, needed for generating the final cross-correlation result tables with the custom R function, since these files contain restricted data that can only be accessed following the instructions, and under the conditions, described in the next paragraphs. The components of the minimum reproducibility package are made available under CC BY 4.0.

The .docx files containing the marking of words by listeners as realizing prosodic functions and the .txt files containing the series of markings derived from these files and the series of effective realization of prosodic functions also derived from these files are not publicly available. This is due to the informed consent form sent to the listeners at the start of this research not providing for data sharing with outside parties. Therefore, any form of data sharing requires approval by the ethics committee and the listeners. Researchers interested in accessing these data can contact the researcher Samuel Sprogis at samuelsprogis@outlook.com and, upon informing the purpose for accessing the data and providing a data-use plan, Samuel will submit an addendum to the process approved by Unicamp's Research Ethics Committee in the Humanities and Social Sciences (Comitê de Ética em Pesquisa em Ciências Humanas e Sociais – CEP-CHS) to allow data sharing with other researchers. If approved by Unicamp's CEP-CHS, all listeners who participated in this research will be recontacted and asked to provide new consent for data sharing. If all listeners consent, the aforementioned .docx and .txt files will be shared with the requesting researcher.

The requesting researcher should know that it takes typically thirty to sixty days for Unicamp's CEP-CHS to respond, and the time to collect new consent from all listeners can vary, but may take up to one month.

The .WAV audio files analyzed in this research and the .WAV audio excerpts, orthographic transcriptions (.docx files), Praat TextGrids and text files (.txt) containing extracted acoustic measures generated from these audio files are also not publicly available. This is due to the audio files having been provided by Plinio A. Barbosa, a member of the third-party project "A typology for word stress and speech rhythm based on acoustic and perceptual considerations", coordinated by Anders Eriksson. Researchers interested in accessing these data can contact the researcher Samuel Sprogis at samuelsprogis@outlook.com and, upon informing the purpose for accessing the data and providing a data-use plan, Samuel will contact Plinio A. Barbosa and ask for permission to share the data under the informed purpose and conditions explained by the data-use plan. If granted permission, Samuel will share the .WAV audio files, .WAV audio excerpts, orthographic transcriptions (.docx files), Praat TextGrids and text files (.txt) containing extracted acoustic measures with the requesting researcher. It may take up to one month for data to be shared.

Reviewers and editors may request access to materials needed for editorial/peer review, including restricted data, via the handling editor in OJS, who will mediate access to the reviewer for the duration of the review process. Within 5 business days of the request, the author will add the handling editor as a read-only collaborator to a private OSF (Open Science Framework) project containing all files required to reproduce the analyses of this research, including de-identified derived data, such as the .txt files containing the series of markings of prosodic functions derived from listeners' annotations and the .txt files containing acoustic measures extracted from the audio files, and aggregated data, such as the .txt files containing the series of effective realization of prosodic functions derived from listeners' annotations, in accordance with ethical constraints. The handling editor may then add the requesting reviewer/editor as a read-only collaborator. Reviewers and editors will receive access only for editorial/peer review purposes and are expected not to store, redistribute, or reuse the data. Temporary access will be provided to the handling editor and requesting reviewer/editor for the duration of the review process; all permissions will be revoked and access will be removed upon the end of the review process.

12. Ethics and Consent

This study was approved by Unicamp's Comitê de Ética em Pesquisa em Ciências Humanas e Sociais (CEP-CHS) (CAAE: 81270924.2.0000.8142). All listeners provided written informed consent before their participation in the research.

13. Disclosure of Funding Sources

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14. AI Use Statement

The author declares that no AI tools were used in the creation of this manuscript or in any part of the work reported.

15. CRediT Contributions

Samuel Sprogis: Conceptualization; Methodology; Software; Formal Analysis; Investigation; Writing – Original Draft; Writing – Review & Editing.

16. Alternative text for figures

Figure 1. This screenshot shows the waveform, spectrogram, orthographic transcription, phonological segmentation and segmentation into V-V units of the word “Morumbi” in Praat.

Figure 2. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters in each lag for the pooled group. Significant correlations indicate increased duration at lag 0 and are consistent with a rising-falling melodic profile.

Figure 3. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters in each lag for the female group. Significant correlations in this figure indicate increased duration at lag 0 and are consistent with a rising-falling melodic profile. The female group shows few significant correlations at lag -1.

Figure 4. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters in each lag for the male group. Significant correlations in this figure indicate increased duration at lag 0 and are consistent with a rising-falling melodic profile.

Figure 5. Image showing the melodic curve in the word “Fevereiro”, along with its phonetic segmentation and segmentation into V-V units, as examples of the patterns reported for terminal boundaries. The melodic curve in this image shows a rise from two V-V units before the stress into the pre-stress V-V unit, followed by a fall at the stress. The segmentation into V-V units shows that the stressed V-V unit is longer than the surrounding units.

Figure 6. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between non-terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters in each lag for the pooled group. Significant correlations indicate increased duration at lags -2 , -1 and 0 and are consistent with a falling-rising melodic profile.

Figure 7. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between non-terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters in each lag for the female group. Significant correlations indicate increased duration at lags -1 and 0 and are consistent with a falling-rising melodic profile.

Figure 8. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between non-terminal boundaries and prosodic parameters in each lag for the male group. Significant correlations indicate increased duration at lags -2 , -1 and 0 and are consistent with a rising melodic profile.

Figure 9. Image showing the melodic curve in the word “Gostava”, along with its phonetic segmentation and segmentation into V-V units, as examples of the patterns reported for non-terminal boundaries. The melodic curve in this image shows a rise at the stressed V-V unit. The segmentation into V-V units shows that the stressed and pre-stress V-V units are longer than the surrounding units.

Figure 10. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between occurrences of narrow informational focus and prosodic parameters in each lag for the pooled group. Significant correlations indicate increased duration at lags -2 , -1 and 0 and are consistent with a rising-falling melodic profile.

Figure 11. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between occurrences of narrow informational focus and prosodic parameters in each lag for the female group. Significant correlations indicate increased duration at lags -1 and 0 and are consistent with a rising-falling melodic profile.

Figure 12. Bar graph of correlation coefficient values between occurrences of narrow informational focus and prosodic parameters in each lag for the male group. Significant correlations indicate increased duration at lags -2 , -1 and 0 and are consistent with a rising-falling melodic profile.

Figure 13. Image showing the melodic curve in the phrase “É bem básico”, along with its phonetic segmentation and segmentation into V-V units, as examples of the patterns reported for occurrences of narrow informational focus. The melodic curve in this image shows a rise at the pre-stress V-V unit, followed by a fall at the stress. The segmentation into V-V units shows that the stressed and pre-stress V-V units are longer than the surrounding units.

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